

RESIN FILLET FORMATION IN HONEYCOMB SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In order to meet the challenges of high production rates for composite structures, an understanding of the relationship between the skin-core interface and heating rate during the curing of sandwich structures is required. This study found that heating rate during cure can affect the size and shape of resin fillets between the skin and the honeycomb core cell walls, but not in a practically significant way. A small effect of heating rate on resin fillet size was seen when heating Hexcel HexPly 8552 UD skinned, Kevlar paper honeycomb cored sandwich structures at 1.5, 6 and 8°C/min. The resin fillet sizes were larger when heated at 1.5 and 6°C/min than those heated at 8°C/min, although there was a large variability of resin fillet sizes. This study concluded that while the effect of heating rate on the skin-core bond needs to be considered, faster heating of composite sandwich structures with epoxy resins and isothermal curing required for automotive production will not greatly affect the skin-core bond.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) provide a lightweight alternative to traditional metallic materials due to their high specific strength and stiffness. Sandwich structure design involves adding a low-density core between the layers of carbon fibre lamina, to increase the stiffness and strength of the panel significantly with minimal weight increase. It is well known that the failure modes of sandwich structures are typically initiated by failure at the interface between the skin and the core [1]. This indicates that a strong skin-core bond allows the load forces to transfer through the skin into the core, resulting in the maximum stiffness that a sandwich structure can achieve [2]. A significant factor that contributes to the skin-core bond when using honeycomb cores, is resin fillet geometry [3-8] (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - A well-formed resin fillet with the different resin fillet geometry displayed.

Resin fillets form at the interface between the face sheet and the honeycomb cell walls as the resin viscosity drops during initial heating of the curing cycle. Viscous resin undergoes capillarity phenomena forming a meniscus between the skin and the honeycomb cell wall. The resin cures in this shape resulting in a resin fillet. A well-formed resin fillet will have a similar height and width, with the fillet area and throat being as large as possible while still maintaining a concave shape. To enable sufficiently sized resin fillets, the viscosity and ability of the resin to wet the core needs to be understood.

The effect of high heating rates on resin viscosity in the production of monolithic carbon fibre composite laminates has been widely studied. Heating rate was shown to affect thermoset resin viscosity dramatically [9, 10] and therefore the flow of resin through a composite [11]. When a thermoset resin is heated at a faster rate, the viscosity drops to a lower point but also initiates the curing reaction earlier, thereby decreasing the processing window [12]. Research focused on the skin-core interface in sandwich structures has been extensive on the subject of the effect of vacuum [13-16], but has been limited to parameter variation of cure temperature profiles. The effect of the resulting resin viscosity on the strength of this bond has not been studied in detail. With increased heating rates, there is more capability to control the viscosity of the resin to help assist void removal [17]. This resin viscosity control can also help with controlling the flow of the resin into the core. Studies have shown that the peel torque increased in the bond when using Quickstep to cure composite sandwich structures compared to autoclave [18, 19].

This study investigates the extent in which the heating rate during processing of Hexcel's HexPly 8552 resin affects the ability of the resin to wet the core material and create different sized or shaped resin fillets.

2 MATERIALS

The skin material used was Hexcel HexPly 8552 UD, a unidirectional IM7 carbon fibre sheet pre-impregnated with Hexcel's 8552 toughened epoxy resin designed for cure at 177°C. Table 1 displays information about the skin material taken from the datasheet. This material was chosen as its low resin content and high viscosity would provide a difference in resin fillet sizes without filling the honeycomb cells with resin, or losing resin from the top skin. It was predicted that resin fillets created would be smaller than those produced when using prepreg purposely designed for the manufacture of sandwich structures, but the principal of the results found would be applicable to all materials.

Properties	HexPly 8552
Prepreg areal weight	270 g/m ²
Resin content (wt.%)	33%
Nominal fibre volume	57.70%

Table 1 - Product information for Hexcel Hexply 8552 unidirectional prepreg [20].

The core material used was manufactured by Schütz. It is a para-aramid fibre paper (Kevlar N636) coated with a heat resistant phenolic resin, in honeycomb form (N636-3.2-48). The density of the core is 48 kg/m³ and has a cell size of 3.2 mm. All cores were cut to size using a knife.

3 LAMINATE MANUFACTURE

Sandwich panels were manufactured at three different heating rates using the Quickstep process; the QS-POC located at Quickstep’s research facility in Bankstown, Australia. The Quickstep process is capable of heating rates of up to 15°C/min and can apply pressure up to 90 kPa (gauge). As the Quickstep process operates at low pressure, it greatly reduces the chance of core crush. The Quickstep process utilizes the increased thermal transfer properties (up to 25 times) of fluid compared to gas. Figure 2 shows a cross sectional view of the Quickstep chamber. The laminate is trapped between a free floating rigid or semi-rigid mould, with a flexible silicone bladder attached to the pressure chamber shell to separate the laminate from the heat transfer fluid. The laminate and mould are “floating” in the heat transfer fluid, resting on the bottom bladder. To heat and compact the laminate for curing, the Quickstep process uses balanced pressure within the heat transfer fluid and the vacuum on the laminate. By clamping the heat transfer fluid filled pressure chambers together when processing, the laminate is compressed while the mould is floating in a balanced pressure environment and therefore is not subject to distortion or stress.

Figure 2 - Quickstep pressure chamber section view and the cure chamber.

The layup of the Hexply 8552 UD prepreg was [(90/0/90/0)C(0/90/0/90)] where C represents the core, with the laminates left under vacuum for 16 hours prior to cure. The vacuum bag arrangement is shown in Figure 3. The cure cycles were ramped straight to the cure temperature of 177°C with no dwell (Table 2). The heating rates used were 1.5, 6 and 8°C/min. Each cure cycle included four panels approximately 240 x 240 mm in size separated by plywood covered in flash tape. Each cure cycle had two panels with a 15 mm core thickness, and two with 25 mm thick cores (Figure 4). The design of the layout was chosen to also understand the variability over a large area (600 x 600 mm) and to enable the results to have industrial relevance. Each panel was given a designation (“Heating rate”-“Core thickness”-“Panel position”) and each panel had three microscopy samples cut from them. The microscopy samples were 20 mm wide to capture 5-7 honeycomb cell walls and taken from the middle and 10-15 mm from each side of the panel. Outlines of the resin fillets were created using Adobe Photoshop. Resin fillet area, height, width and throat were measured by using Adobe Photoshop’s measurement tool.

Figure 3 – Vacuum bag arrangement for debulking and curing.

Step	Slow heating rate	Medium heating rate	Fast heating rate
1	Apply full vacuum.	Apply full vacuum.	Apply full vacuum.
2	Apply cure chamber pressure of 60 kPa.	Apply cure chamber pressure of 60 kPa.	Apply cure chamber pressure of 60 kPa.
3	Heat at 1.5°C/min to 177°C.	Heat at 6°C/min to 177°C.	Heat at 8°C/min to 177°C.
4	Hold at 177°C for 30 minutes.	Hold at 177°C for 20 minutes.	Hold at 177°C for 20 minutes.
5	Cool at maximum rate.	Cool at maximum rate.	Cool at maximum rate.

Table 2 - Curing procedures for panels manufactured for the initial study in the QS-POC.

Figure 4 – Panel layout for the three different cures used. T# represents thermocouple positioning.

4 RESIN FILLET ANALYSIS

The resin fillet measurements (area, throat, height and width) for each cure cycle were compared using IBM SPSS Statistics 22. The resin fillets from the panels cured using the 8°C/min heating rate were statistically smaller (Kruskal-Wallis analysis with a 95% confidence level) than fillets in panels heated at 1.5°C/min and 6°C/min for all four different resin fillet geometry measurements. This difference was more pronounced for the resin fillet areas and heights. Figure 5 displays the box plots comparing the medians and ranges of the resin fillet geometries when cured at the different heating rates.

Boxplots were used to display the data as the Shapiro-Wilk method found that the data was not normally distributed and, therefore, boxplots are the best method for comparing distributions. The boxplots displayed in this paper are configured so that the bottom of the box represents the 25th percentile, the middle bar represents the median, and the top of the box represents the 75th percentile. The whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum resin fillet sizes. The smaller error bars extended from the median show the limits of the confidence interval. Plots marked with asterisks differ from those without an asterisk in the same plot, when analysed with a 95% confidence level.

Figure 5 – Resin fillet height measurements against the temperature ramp rates used to cure the panels.

The width/height ratios were also calculated. There was a statistical difference between the width/height ratios for panels using a fast heating rate compared to panels that were manufactured using a slow heating rate. In Figure 6 it can be seen that resin fillets produced with the faster heating rate tended to have a wider ratio, indicating that the resin did not wick into the core as far. This means the height is more affected by heating rate and was the sole focus for analyzing the effect different variables had on the resin fillet size.

Figure 6 - The width/height ratios displayed via boxplot for the temperature ramp rates used to cure the panels.

Independent variables were isolated to understand their effects on resin fillet height. Non-parametric tests via independent sample analysis indicated that there were statistical differences between the resin fillet sizes in different panels, the top and bottom skins, and the location of the sample on the panel.

The difference in resin fillet size between panels is related to the cure cycle, but also displays any outliers that would affect the difference across heating rates. A comparison between the resin fillet height medians using Kruskal-Wallis with a 95% confidence level showed that panels F-15-R, F-25-L and F-25-R (cured with a heating rate of 8°C/min) were all statistically smaller than panel S-25-L from the 1.5°C/min cure and panel M-25-L from the 5°C/min cure. The boxplots of the resin fillet heights for different panels is shown in Figure 7. These results strengthen the overall results seen for the difference in resin fillet size for heating rates.

Figure 7 - Boxplots of resin fillet heights in each panel. Panels marked with asterisks differ from those marked only with a hash.

The top skin fillet heights were statistically larger than the bottom skins, but a practically insignificant difference of approximately a 5% increase in height from bottom skin to top skin (Figure 8). This result suggests that gravity has a small effect on resin fillet height as it is impeding the resin wicking up the honeycomb cell walls from the bottom skin, and aiding the top skin resin wicking in to the core.

Figure 8 - Boxplots showing that the top skin has statistically significantly larger fillet heights than the bottom skin.

A difference in resin fillet height between sample locations is a result of manufacturing inconsistency across the area of the lay-up. The slight differences are shown in Figure 9 with the sample location in the middle of the panels having smaller fillets. This suggests some variability across the cure chamber in temperature and pressure, the extent of which this variability affects resin fillet formation will be explored in future work.

Figure 9 – Boxplots of resin fillet heights at different sample locations on the sandwich structures. A statistical difference was only found between location 1 and 3.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study found that using a faster heating rate when curing honeycomb cored sandwich structures with epoxy resin as the skin matrix results in slightly smaller resin fillets. Heating rate has a more pronounced effect on fillet height, with the resin not wicking into the core as far. This could mean that the resin is reaching its gelation point faster and not allowing the resin to wick into the core prior to curing. Further analysis of the cure kinetics and rheology of Hexcel 8552 resin and the variability of the fillets across the cure chamber will be conducted to provide a further understanding of the extent of the effect of heating rate on resin fillet formation.

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